

Stratigraphic Paleobiology of Carbonate Systems: Supplementary Materials

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Simulation Setup

Simulation studies are primarily dependent on simulation parameters (constants) and logic, not data. Accordingly, we do not save any generated data but rather ensure computational reproducibility by versioning and documenting dependencies. In Julia, this is done via the included package manager and the *Project.toml* and *Manifest.toml* files. In R, we use the *renv* package (Ushey and Wickham 2026).

The setup consists of two steps:

1. Simulation of carbonate platforms in Julia. This saves data locally in hdf5, exports sediment accumulation curves, age-depth models, and water depths as .csv files for further processing in R, and generates figures of the simulated platforms
2. Processing and simulation in R: This imports the .csv files into R and produces all figures. All simulation code is encapsulated in the plotting functions. This avoids inconsistencies between generated data and plots, allows for easy modification and exploration of the large parameter space by users, and avoids spillover of variables between different simulation procedures.

In both cases, constants that determine system behavior and the parts of parameter space explored are isolated into separate file to allow easy modification of the general setup. These files are *code/constants.jl* (Julia) and *code/load_data_and_constants.R* (R). Detailed instructions for the reproduction of the study are available in the REPRODUCEME.md file under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20670764> (Hohmann et al. 2026).

Initial Topographies

CarboKitten.jl allows users to start simulation from arbitrary initial topographies. A common choice for attached depositional systems are simple ramp geometries (Hohmann et al. 2024; Zimmit et al. 2021). However, this computationally convenient choice does usually not reflect the geometry of the depositional system in (quasi) steady state, where accumulation and subsidence balance out. A typical artefact of implausible starting geometries in carbonate platforms is a rapid initial progradation, as shallow water locations are quickly filled by the rapidly growing euphotic factory (e.g., Supplementary Figure 1).

To reduce these temporal edge effects, we use pre-runs to generate the initial topographies of our main simulation runs used for the analysis. Pre-runs are 1 Myr in duration under constant sea level, while all other parameters are kept identical to the main runs. This is enough time for both depositional systems to develop their characteristic geometry, which we then use as initial topography for the main simulation runs. For details on the implementation, see the supplementary code.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Pre-run of the platform geometry simulation under constant sea level.

Supplementary Figure 2: Pre-run of the ramp geometry simulation under constant sea level.

Supplementary Figure 3: Sediment profile (A), Wheeler (chronostratigraphic) diagram (B) and sea level curve (C) of the platform geometry simulation with sampling locations and systems tracts. See Figure 1 for a side-by-side view of the platform and ramp geometry.

Supplementary Figure 4: Sediment profile (A), Wheeler (chronostratigraphic) diagram (B) and sea level curve (C) of the ramp geometry simulation with systems tracts and sampling locations highlighted. See Figure 1 for a side-by-side view of the platform and ramp geometry.

Supplementary Figure 5: Sedimentation rates in the platform and ramp simulation in the time domain, averaged over 100 kyr.

Supplementary Figure 6: Stratigraphic completeness in the platform and ramp simulation, measured over increments of 1 kyr (model resolution).

Supplementary Figure 7: Frequency of hiatus durations at the 5 examined locations. At 18 km in the ramp geometry, there is only one hiatus, which is why no kernel density estimate is shown.

Supplementary Figure 8: Number of hiatuses in the ramp and platform simulation.

Supplementary Figure 9: Thickness of sections in the ramp and platform simulation. The dashed line indicates the limit on section thickness imposed by subsidence.

Supplementary Figure 10: Maximum, median, 1st and 3rd quartile of the distribution of hiatus durations along the onshore-offshore gradient. Statistics were calculated every 0.75 km.

Supplementary Figure 11: Cumulative relative proportion of time vs cumulative proportion of height in the platform and ramp geometries.

Supplementary Figure 12: Water depth in the time domain. See Figure 3 for water depth in the stratigraphic domain.

Supplementary Figure 13: Extinction scenarios used in the simulation. Extinction rates were rescaled to produce 1000 extinctions over the simulated 4 Myr to reduce random fluctuations and artifacts introduced by small sample sizes.

A Platform, 3 km from Shore

B Platform, 7.5 km from Shore

C Platform, 10.5 km from Shore

D Platform, 12 km from Shore

E Platform, 18 km from Shore

Supplementary Figure 14: Clusters of last occurrences as a function of sampling rate in the platform simulation assuming a constant background extinction rate.

Supplementary Figure 15: Clusters of last occurrences as a function of sampling rate in the ramp simulation, assuming a constant background extinction rate.

Supplementary Figure 17: Preservation of extinctions in different systems tracts in the ramp geometry. Sampling rate is 10 fossils per Myr.

Supplementary Figure 18: Spatial correlation of extinctions in different systems tracts in the platform geometry. Sampling rate is 30 fossils per Myr.

Supplementary Figure 19: Spatial correlation of extinctions in the ramp geometry under different extinction scenarios. Sampling rate is 30 fossils per Myr.

Supplementary Figure 20: Transition from platform to ramp geometry. The simulation setup combines a pre-run with platform parameters (see above) with a 4 Myr main run with ramp parameters (see Supplementary Code (Hohmann et al. 2026)).

Supplementary Figure 21: Transition from ramp to platform geometry. The simulation setup combines a pre-run with ramp parameters (see above) with a 4 Myr main run with platform parameters (see Supplementary Code ((Hohmann et al. 2026))).

References

- Hohmann, Niklas, Anna Jansen, Sidney Bickerton, Xianyi Liu, and Emilia Jarochowska. 2026. *Stratigraphic Paleobiology of Carbonate Systems: Supplementary Code*. V. 1.0.1. Zenodo, released June 12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.20670764>.
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